

AN EYE on PHARMACEUTICAL INDUSTRIES - BLOCKCHAIN TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract: Greetings and welcome to this perceptive investigation into how block chain technology can transform the pharmaceutical industry's traceability and transparency.¹ In order to track medications from the point of manufacture to the point of patient delivery, the pharmaceutical industry has adopted the suggested system. The effects of a medication are documented in a database for later statistical analysis after it is used by the patient.² Ultimately, the study's primary goals are to reduce manual labor in the supply chain's with most efficient architecture and raise the safety of pharmaceutical products.³

Key words: Traceability, transparency, security, visuability, pharmaceutical supply chain.

I. INTRODUCTION

Consider distributing a digital journal among many users in a network. Blockchain functions on a decentralized principle, in contrast to a traditional diary where one person has the only pen. The same journal is owned by several users, and any addition or change is approved by all of them before it is made permanent.¹ A blockchain is an open ledger to which anybody can gain access, but it is not controlled by a single entity.² It is a technology that makes it possible for people and businesses to work together transparently and with trust. Block chains, sometimes referred to as peer-to-peer networks, are simply distributed organizations that share and agree upon a conveyed information base.³ In the pharmaceutical industry, supply chain management is the process that ensures drugs are successfully delivered to patients. These days, a supply chain may span multiple geological regions and hundreds of stages. Typically a supply chain consists of several participants such as manufacturer's, suppliers, transporters, whole-saler's, distributors, retailers, etc making it complex, spanning over space and time.⁴ The manufacture and sale of counterfeit drugs is a serious global problem that is becoming more urgent, particularly in developing nations. The annual market value of counterfeit pharmaceuticals has grown to billions of dollars. The pharmaceutical industry's flawed supply chain system is one of the causes of drug counterfeiting.⁵ With capital investments in blockchain technology predicted to reach USD 13.96 billion by 2022, blockchain is an ideal solution for creating a safe drug supply chain where the two main issues are privacy and data security.⁶ The threat caused by counterfeit medications to society is severe. False medications have a direct or indirect negative impact on patients' health, sometimes leading to major problems and even death.⁷ Consumer safety is at risk from counterfeit medications, which are thought to be the cause of over a million deaths annually, according to INTERPOL estimates. In addition, there is a growing mistrust of the pharmaceutical industry; a recent study found that seven out of ten consumers fear that they will receive medical products that are tainted, mislabeled, handled carelessly, or counterfeited.⁸ It is advised that blockchain be implemented to address important problems facing the healthcare industry, such as data privacy laws compliance and safe record sharing. Data is stored and registered using cryptographic signatures and consensus algorithms, which are used as essential enablers in their application.⁹ The supply of pharmaceutical products and their tracking may be reliably protected legally by using block chain technology in pharmacy. Block chain technology has the potential to boost patient safety, increase privacy and confidentiality, streamline operations, and give consumers access to more advanced clinical care, particularly in the pharmacy and healthcare sectors.¹⁰

II. WORKING OF BLOCKCHAIN TECHNOLOGY

Let us look at how the blockchain network works and how it might help to tackle the problem of drug counterfeiting. All that blockchain is a set of nodes sharing a distributed, immutable database over a peer-to-peer network. On this network, every action is referred to as a transaction. A group of such transactions forms a block. A block is linked to the hash value, hash of the previous block, and a timestamp. The ledger is impervious to manipulation and unchangeable due to the interlocking of its blocks.

The Proof-of-Work consensus or any other custom consensus algorithm that verifies the blocks is added to the network, giving the blockchain network accountability and integrity. Blockchain is the best option for resolving supply chain management system traceability issues because it can store transactions according to their order. The manufacturer will first generate a QR code with the following information: the transaction number, manufacturing date, expiration date, and manufacturer's name. The transaction number will aid in the identification of the medicine on the blockchain. The distributor will then verify the code's validity by scanning it. The distributor must affix his signature to the medication's record as soon as the shipment leaves his storage. At their end, pharmacies, retailers, and wholesalers will all

perform the same duties. Tracking and traceability in the drug supply chain can be achieved by documenting transactions at every point of the chain.³

III. HISTORY

The creator of Bitcoin, the first cryptocurrency in history, Satoshi Nakamoto, is a mysterious individual or group that popularized BCT (Nakamoto, 2008). Nakamoto (Nakamoto, 2008) presented the idea of developing a decentralized, cryptographically-secured currency that enables financial transactions in a white paper titled "Bitcoin: A peer-to-peer electronic cash system." The primary technological advancement of the Bitcoin protocol lies in its capacity to resolve the issue of double-spending and facilitate electronic money transfers without requiring the involvement of a central authority, such as banks, for transaction authorization (Hanley, 2018).

A "digital, decentralized, and distributed ledger in which transactions are logged and added in chronological order with the goal of creating permanent and tamperproof records" is how Treiblmaier (Treiblmaier, 2018) defines blockchain (BC) (p. 574). In order to handle a wide range of business use cases, BC is not a single technology but rather a collection of various technologies, tools, and techniques (Rejeb et al., 2018; Treiblmaier, 2019; Rejeb et al., 2020).¹¹

A blockchain and Internet of Things (IoT) pharma supply chain was proposed by Jianfeng Shi et al. to guarantee the legitimacy of data sources, IoT devices, sensors, locators, and QR codes. In order to maintain data transparency and improve product safety, a distributed ledger was implemented for data sharing and storage. A technique called Gcoin was proposed by Yen-Chih Liao, Bin Chong, Jen-Hung Tseng, and Shih-Wei Liao. The foundation of the drug data flow is blockchain. Transparent drug transactions are ensured by an open government model combined with a decentralized autonomous organization regulation model. A blockchain-based solution was proposed by Haya Hasana, Esra AlHadhramia, Alia Al Dhaheri, Khaled Salaha, and Raja Jayaraman. This solution made use of the Ethereum blockchain's smart contract features.³

IV. TYPES OF BLOCK CHAIN TECHNOLOGY

A. Public Blockchain

A public Blockchain is a permission-less Blockchain that is accessible to the general public. I.e. A public blockchain is a decentralized platform that enables anybody to join the network and approve transactions there. As an illustration, consider Litecoin, Ethereum, and Bitcoin.

B. Private Blockchain

Restrictive or permissioned blockchains that function exclusively within private networks are known as private blockchains. It is typically applied in a company where only a limited number of people are part of the Blockchain network. Ripple and Hyperledger are two examples.

C. Hybrid Blockchain

The features of a public (permission-less) and private (permissioned) blockchain are combined in a hybrid blockchain. Customized to industry needs, hybrid blockchain is developed based on a variety of business needs. Organizations can control who has access to data stored on the Blockchain and what information is made public by using it to create both a private, permission-based system and a public, permission-less system. Take IBM Food Trust, for instance.

D. Consortium Blockchain

The transactions are carried out by Consortium Blockchain utilizing both public and private blockchains. They do not allow third parties to validate transactions and are run by a limited group of participants. Transactions may be written by any member of a particular group, but they can be read by the general public. Hyperledger Fabric is one example.¹²

V. REAL WORLD EXAMPLES

- MedRec uses blockchain technology to create an auditable record of patient-provider interactions within the context of electronic health records. This improves accessibility, privacy, and data accuracy, enabling people to make well-informed medical decisions.
- VeChain, a blockchain-based supply chain solution, partnered with a major pharmaceutical company to enhance traceability in its supply chain. By enabling customers to confirm a product's authenticity, the partnership seeks to stop fake medications from reaching the market.¹

VI. BLOCKCHAIN TECHNOLOGY IN PHARMA

A. Clinical Trials

Blockchain can ensure the authenticity and accuracy of results by bringing clinical trial data to a previously unheard-of level of transparency. Trust between stakeholders can be fostered by immutable records, which can validate patient consent, data integrity, and protocol adherence.

B. Regulatory Compliance

Blockchain technology can simplify the difficult process of regulatory compliance with its automated verification mechanisms. Companies can speed up audits and ensure compliance with global standards by creating a secure, tamper-proof repository of regulatory documents.

C. Personalized Medicine

The ability of blockchain to securely store and share patient data may aid in the development of personalized treatment plans. Patients can control access to their medical history, empowering them to contribute to research while safeguarding their privacy.

D. Supply Chain Innovation

Beyond transparency, supply chain optimization can benefit from blockchain technology. By enabling predictive analytics, supply chain interruptions can be reduced, inventory control can be facilitated, and demand forecasting can be made easier.¹

VII. PROJECTS IN BLOCKCHAIN TECHNOLOGY IN PHARMA

A. Merck blockchain project

In order to test a multi-phase blockchain project, Merck teamed up with Animal Ventures, a young technology consultancy, in 2017. The project aims to create a new global logistics framework for pharmaceutical supply chains that provides a number of small solutions that together give industry supply chains increased speed, dependability, security, and agility instead of a single, all-encompassing solution.

B. MediLedger project

Through the use of the Ethereum blockchain and permissioned controls that prohibit the double transfer of a serialized unit, the MediLedger project, which was introduced by Chronicled Technologies in 2017, seeks to prove compliance with the Drug Supply Chain Security Act (DSCSA) of 2013. In order to accomplish this, Chronicled is setting up electronic standards that track and identify specific prescription medications as they travel through the country's pharmaceutical supply chains.

C. Yijian blockchain project

In the beginning of 2017, IBM and Sichuan Hejia Co., Ltd. collaborated to introduce the Yijian blockchain technology application system, a blockchain financial services project for pharmaceutical procurement. The Hyperledger Fabric, upon which Yijian is based, was created with permissioned controls to enhance supply chain finance's operations, efficiency, and transparency.¹³

VIII. BLOCKCHAINS AND DLI'S

Blockchain is a kind of internet-based distributed ledger infrastructure (DLI) and communications protocol. It was first intended to serve as the foundational framework for the cryptocurrency known as Bitcoin, which is based on a combination of game theory, economics, and computer science. A paradigm shift in the way we input, store, retrieve, and exchange value over the internet is represented by blockchains and other DLIs. Most significantly, as autonomous and intelligent machines start to power our trade, supply chain, and pharmaceutical networks, it will become more and more important that blockchains and other DLIs are designed to be decentralized, meaning that all infrastructure decisions are not centrally governed by any one entity.¹³

Centralization or decentralization? To be honest, why would you not trust your government or the Ministry of Health to keep your information private? Blockchain, in theory, states that establishments should be decentralized by removing the center of gravity. Still, we find nothing particularly inspiring about decentralization. In the unlikely event that we use any platforms, we will essentially delegate work to excavators and hubs without delving deeply into the pros and cons of centralization vs decentralization. Therefore, a solution will be deemed equivalent whether it is integrated or decentralized.³

IX. PHARMACEUTICAL SUPPLY CHAIN; COUNTERFEITING IN PHARMACEUTICAL SUPPLY CHAIN

Counterfeit drugs have long been a major concern. Over 200 billion USD are thought to be exchanged in the counterfeit market. Drugs that are "manufactured fraudulently, mislabelled, with low quality, hiding the source detail or identity, and do not follow the defined standard, are considered to be fake or counterfeits," according to the World Health Organization.¹² Because of its transparent nature and tamper-proof records, blockchain makes it very difficult for counterfeiters to enter the supply chain. By following the origins of their medications on the blockchain, consumers can confirm that they are authentic. This empowers patients to make informed decisions about the products they consume.¹

X. DIGITILIZATION OF PHARMACEUTICAL SECTOR

Pharmaceuticals (medication, immunizations, and consumables) are now transported via a rigid, pre-planned supply chain from an industrial manufacturer to a retail customer (patient). Safe transportation is this department's primary responsibility. The number of fake medications entering the healthcare industry is steadily increasing. In the majority of developing countries, one out of every ten medical products is counterfeit. These medications either contain the incorrect medical ingredient or lack an active ingredient.

Today, in connection with the COVID-19 pandemic, more and more attention are focused on the transportation of medicines. The British Broadcasting Channel (BBC) News conducted an investigation that revealed the sale of fake medications in Africa. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), using these medications may result in "serious side effects". This is because, first, all sensor data recorded during direct transportation can be stored using blockchain technology, and second, no party involved in the relationship can alter these readings within the system. .. As a result, the digital health logistics ecosystem will become more trustworthy as Blockchain technology is used.

In transit, the smart box sensor can quickly gather temperature data and send it to the blockchain, ensuring that the data is securely stored and ready for validation and inspection.¹⁴

XI. IMPLEMENTATION

In order to integrate blockchain technology into the pharmaceutical supply chain system, it is necessary to first comprehend the inner workings of the blockchain ledger. Blockchain includes a cryptographically secure key pair as part of its built-in identity mechanism (see the section above). These keys are used to allocate a certain network activity to each member. A participant might be a gadget, a person, or an entity. These keys reveal the original identities of the players. Although a key pair doesn't reveal anything about the participant, it can be linked to other details (such as name, contact information,

or professional qualifications). However, the optimal course of action is to retain these extra pieces of information off-chain and use their IDs to merge them with on-chain data (key pair). Manufacturers, packers, distributors, physicians, and other relevant parties will all be involved in the management of the pharmaceutical supply chain. These individuals will all be recognized by their distinct key pair on the network. Drugs will be regarded as the assets, and they will all have distinct keys (or hashes). The medication will have an ID attached to it in the form of a QR Code. There are now just a few different kinds of blockchain networks on the market, such as the original Bitcoin Blockchain, Ethereum, Hyperledger, and BigchainDB. However, the Ethereum permissioned blockchain is the one we recommend.²

Zuellig Pharma, one of Asia's largest healthcare services groups, developed a PSC solution, i.e., eZTracker, based on the proposed framework. The eZTracker blockchain network provides a platform for non-intrusive data sharing and exchange amongst various PSC parties, including as distributors, manufacturers, and HCPs. Delivery, storage, dispensing, and other tasks can be easily tagged against distinct, serialized pharmaceutical items thanks to the network. HCPs and patients can use eZTracker to confirm the provenance and legitimacy of medications at the box or batch level. The high-level design of the eZTracker system is displayed.⁸

XII. LEGAL IMPLEMENTATION OF BLOCKCHAIN TECHNOLOGY IN PHARMACY:

The study of legal aspects of preventing the spread of falsified medicines is highly relevant from both theoretical and practical point of view. Blockchain technology in pharmacy could offer trustworthy legal protection for medicinal product delivery and tracking.

Directive 2011/62/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of June 8, 2011 amending Directive 2001/83 / EC on the Community code relating to medicinal products for human use in respect of the prevention of the entry of falsified medicinal products into the legal supply chain provides the legal foundation for the introduction of blockchain technology in pharmacy. This document, which came into force on January 2013, stipulates that the manufacturer can mark drugs registered in the country with the unique identifier.¹⁰

XIII. CHALLENGES IN BLOCKCHAIN TECHNOLOGY

Today's major PSC issues include cold chain monitoring, sales rechanneling, counterfeiting, traceability, inefficient product recalls, and inadequate inventory management. Due to the PSC's inherent complexity, implementing solutions to address these issues in a trustworthy, secure, efficient, and traceable manner continues to be challenging.

- Data Fragmentation Impedes Traceability
- Growing Counterfeit Markets
- Lack of Cold Chain Monitoring
- Sales Rechanneling Activities
- Ineffective Product Recalls
- Poor Product Expiration and Shortage Management.⁸

Before blockchain is able to achieve mass-adoption, the following elements will need to be considered:

A. Governance

Ensuring that blockchain technology complies with current standards, particularly HIPAA, and developing new ones specifically for this innovation. A strong governance model is also required to guarantee that the network is genuinely decentralized, trustworthy, and effective—especially when deploying autonomous and intelligent machines—because once data is placed on a blockchain, it becomes the property of the network.

B. Scalability

The current state of blockchain technology is not scalable enough to record transactions at the same speed as the automated machinery used in medicine distribution and manufacturing.

C. Interoperability

Often times, blockchain systems are not compatible with each other. In a closed ecosystem, such as that of the pharmaceutical industry, stakeholders and participants are highly reliant on each other. It is imperative that a single blockchain technology be widely used in order to ensure uniformity and communication throughout the supply chain.¹³

D. Supply Chain Transparency

Blockchain's decentralized nature ensures that every participant has real-time access to an immutable record of each transaction. In the pharmaceutical industry, this refers to following a medication from the time it is first developed as raw materials until it is administered to patients. Blockchain allows for the accurate identification of impacted products, hence minimizing the impact on patients in the event that a batch of pharmaceuticals needs to be recalled due to quality concerns.

E. Counterfeit Drug Prevention

It is very difficult for counterfeiters to penetrate the supply chain because to blockchain's tamper-proof records and transparent structure. Consumers can validate the legitimacy of their pharmaceuticals by tracing their origins on the blockchain. This empowers patients to make informed decisions about the products they consume.

F. Data Integrity

Data integrity must be maintained in clinical trials and research. The immutability of blockchain guarantees the accuracy and non-reversibility of research findings, patient data, and clinical trial results. The public, regulators, and researchers all gain confidence as a result.

G. Streamlined Regulatory Compliance

The automation of data gathering and verification with blockchain technology enhances the efficiency of complying with intricate regulatory criteria. Audits are enhanced in speed and accuracy when all required paperwork is safely kept on the blockchain.¹

XIV. USES

A. Transparency

Each participant has an identical copy of all the information. The consent of the majority of nodes is required before any transaction blocks can be added to the ledger. By enabling companies to track every aspect of the system, this increases openness and gets rid of fraud.¹² In a blockchain network, all members have equal access to all data. All parties may view transactions, which promotes great transparency and lessens the possibility of fraudulent activity.¹

B. Security

Because no one can easily alter the network's attributes to their benefit, blockchain technology eliminates the need for central authority. Since every piece of information on the Blockchain is cryptographically hashed, the system is more protected.¹²

The network's processing capacity may suffer when one party holds 51 percent of the vote. A damaged healthcare system will cause healthcare organizations to lose their reputation, thus this is a critical issue that needs to be addressed.¹⁶

Blockchain secures data by using cryptographic methods, which improve defenses against unwanted access. Protecting sensitive patient information and intellectual property is especially important in the pharmaceutical industry.¹

C.Traceability

It is possible to track a product or piece of information through its whole journey because blockchain records are unchangeable and chronological. This involves tracking the source of raw materials, production methods, distribution, and even patient usage in the pharmaceutical industry.¹

D.Health care

As we speak, one of the worst and most widespread COVID-19 pandemics in history is affecting the entire world. Medical staff and facilities needed to mobilize quickly to deal with these infections by utilizing all available resources.¹²

E. Visibility and protect privacy

The majority of the time, visibility and privacy go hand in hand, and obtaining one often means losing the other. Block chain technology is the best available for trade because it can guarantee the authenticity of data made publicly available while maintaining the privacy and confidentiality of an entity's private information. The goods in a pharmaceutical supply chain system can be independently verified without revealing the manufacturer's secret manufacturing processes. However, various network users will have access to the patient's medical record without being aware of the patient's personal information.²

F. Data base for future statistics

When a doctor is recommending a dose to a patient in the future, the record of the patient's drug reaction will be helpful. Patients' privacy was at risk when using traditional databases for this kind of record-keeping, but with block chains, patient data can be stored without revealing his personal information.²

XV. LIMITATIONS

- A significant change has occurred in the health care industry with the introduction of BCT, which presents a number of creative applications and use cases but also creates new difficulties.¹¹
- The study's methodology, which focuses on the pharmaceutical supply chain, could be its drawback.¹⁵
- Research addressing these issues is necessary, and the introduction of more scalable BCs is imperative.¹¹
- Even though the solution has been effectively implemented in some markets, the pharmaceutical industry still faces difficulties in making enterprise blockchain a standard solution.⁸

XVI. FUTURE SCOPE

The pharmaceutical supply chain is the main focus of the study's methodology. Future research ought to concentrate on different sectors.¹⁵ Improved pharmaceutical supply chain management and traceability are critical needs that have been brought to our attention.¹² The potential of BC is expected to enhance patient autonomy over medical records, streamline healthcare procedures, and eventually boost the standard of care provided.¹¹ Future research may look at factors like transaction throughput, consensus mechanism, block propagation rate, and block size that affect how flexible BC healthcare systems.¹¹ By implementing an auto-replenishment function, pharmaceutical manufacturers can expedite the inventory turnaround of products from warehouses, improve their recall management, and obtain additional insights into HCPs' product stock-out status. Digitally connecting manufacturers to their interlinked businesses will be an essential aspect of PSC's future.⁸ Before being implemented, supply chains based on blockchain technology need more study. To increase effectiveness, security, and user-friendliness, more features can be included. Introducing further notice characteristics use QRcode to maintain track of goods, adding more security to the data. Other products that require traceability and monitoring throughout their lifecycle can also make use of this system.⁷

XVII. CONCLUSION

We presented an additional blockchain use case in this paper.²The pharmaceutical industry's supply chain lacks a suitable traceability system, which contributes to the rise in counterfeit medications and makes it difficult to find them.³It is now clear how crucial transparency and traceability are, and how much of an impact they have on patient safety, legal compliance, and overall operational excellence.¹The goal of utilizing distributed ledgers to digitize domestic healthcare is to create higher-quality medical products. It leads to the improvement of the entire structure and advances the development of the relevant sector.¹⁴Blockchain technology ensures transparent delivery and lowers logistics costs while lowering the danger of giving patients counterfeit drugs. As a result, patients pay less for the finished product.¹⁰The goal of this research project is to better understand how blockchain technology is applied.¹⁶

REFERENCES

1. <https://www.qualifyze.com/resources/blog/the-role-of-blockchain-technology-in-pharma/>
2. Ijazul Haq, Olivier Muselemu Esuka. *Blockchain Technology in Pharmaceutical Industry to Prevent Counterfeit Drugs*. International Journal of Computer Applications. MARCH 2018;180:8-12.
3. Vishwesh Lingayat, Isha Pardikar, Shubham Yewalekar, Shyamal Khachane, Sachin Pande. *Securing Pharmaceutical Supply Chain using Blockchain Technology*. ITM Web of Conferences 37, 2021; 01013ICITSD.1-7.
4. Agya Pathak, Sameer Shrivastava, Palempati Harsha Vardhini, Abhinay Meka, Divesh Swami, Zakir Hussain et al. *Blockchain Technology in Pharmaceutical Supply Chain Management*. International Conference on Computational Intelligence and Communication Networks (CICN), 2022.
5. Leo van Moergestel, Ander de Keijzer. *Blockchain Technology and Applications*, 2105. <https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-2105/10000439.pdf>
6. T. Poongodi, S. Sudhakar Ilango, Vaishali Gupta, Sanjeev Kumar Prasad. *Influence of blockchain technology in pharmaceutical industries*. May 2022; 267-296.
7. Sheetal Nayak, Prachitee Shirvale, Nihar Naik, Snehpriya Khul, Amol Sawant. *Blockchain-Enabled Drug Supply Chain*. May 2021; 1:41-44.
8. Yan Pang, Zhen Yu, Haisheng Zhang, Corinne Sim, Marianne Louise Chang, Ashley Chong. *Blockchain Technology Transforms the Pharmaceutical Supply Chain*. SSRN;1-16.
9. Umair Bashir, Aiesha Ahmad, Shafia Riaz, Maheen Ilyas, Wajahat Anwaar Bukhari. *Blockchain technology in healthcare: A systematic review*. April 2022; <https://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0266462>.
10. Vitalii Pashkov, Oleksii Soloviov. *Legal implementation of blockchain technology in pharmacy*. SHS Web of Conferences 68. 2018; 01027;1-8.
11. Abderahman Rejeb, Horst Treiblmaier, Karim Rejeb, Suhaiza Zailani. *Blockchain research in healthcare: a bibliometric review and current research trends*. *Journal of Data, Information and Management*. 2021;3:109–124.
12. Jayendra S Jadhav, Jyoti Deshmukh. *A review study of the blockchain-based healthcare supply chain*. *Social Sciences & Humanities Open*, 2022; 6:1-15.
13. https://medium.com/@j_35377/blockchain-in-pharma-4e448b7a656b.
14. Ahad Qodirov. *Blockchain technology for digitalization of the pharmaceutical sector of the Russian Federation*. E3S Web of Conferences 2021; 02028;1-9.
15. Arash Kordestani, Pejvak Oghazi, Rana Mostaghel. *Smart contract diffusion in the pharmaceutical blockchain: the battle of counterfeit drugs*. *Journal of Business Research*, 2023; 158;1-10
16. Huma Saeed, Hassaan Malik, Umair Bashir, Aiesha Ahmad, Shafia Riaz, Maheen Ilyas. *Blockchain technology in healthcare: A systematic review*, plusone; april 2022. <https://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0266462>.